

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Deliverable 7.3

Report on Dissemination Activities

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Deliverable 7.3

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIoD	AI-on-Demand
CTAs	Calls to Action
CV	Curriculum Vitae
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Commission
HRM	Human Resources Managers
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NL	National Labs
RTOs	Research and Technology Organizations
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

This document outlines the communication and dissemination activities undertaken under the BIAS project's Work Package 7 (WP7), covering Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation from November 2022 to October 2024. The primary goal is to provide a comprehensive account of the key materials, channels, tools, and activities used by the BIAS consortium during this period.

Throughout these two years, the BIAS project has implemented an extensive dissemination strategy to promote its objectives, activities, research outcomes, and societal impact. By leveraging various channels and activities, BIAS engages a diverse set of stakeholders, including AI developers, Human Resources Managers (HRM), policymakers, advocates, and the general public, fostering a fairer use of AI in the labour market.

The project utilizes a range of communication channels to disseminate its research findings and engage with stakeholders. The BIAS website serves as a central information hub, attracting over 32,592 views and 8,992 active users from 108 countries. Regular updates through email newsletters, website articles, and accessible materials—such as factsheets, infographics, and videos—ensure stakeholders remain informed about project developments and events.

Social media is a crucial component of BIAS's communication strategy. The project actively engages with its audience on platforms including Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, and more recently, Instagram and Telegram. With a growing social media following of over 1,272 individuals, BIAS effectively reaches a broad audience, generating over 3,917 cumulative audience reactions. The use of accessible and inclusive language ensures that the project's outcomes are communicated to all target audiences.

The BIAS consortium collaborates closely with various AI and HRM organizations, as well as related research projects. Key achievements include the creation of the AI Fairness Cluster, the development of the Trustworthy AI Helix, and interaction with the AI-on-Demand (AIoD) platform. Consortium members also actively participate in and co-organize high-level scientific conferences, workshops, symposiums, and webinars. Through these activities, BIAS engages with the AI research and HRM industries, contributing to both academic discourse and practical industry applications.

The project also aims to raise awareness among the general public. By producing videos, accessible knowledge resources, social media polls, and blog posts, BIAS encourages public participation in AI-related discussions and activities.

BIAS's dissemination strategy spans a wide range of activities and communication channels to reach diverse stakeholders and promote the responsible use of AI in the labour market. During the first year, the focus was on building awareness and establishing a community of stakeholders and target

groups. In the second year, the emphasis shifted to deepening audience engagement, showcasing preliminary results, increasing web traffic, and enhancing social media presence. This phase has been crucial for fostering a stronger connection with the audience and building a supportive community around the project. By engaging with this community, BIAS contributes to advancing a fairer use of AI tools in the labour market, promoting a trustworthy and inclusive AI ecosystem in Europe. Through collaborative efforts and innovative research, BIAS is poised to make a significant and lasting impact on both the labour market and society as a whole.

2. Introduction

Because AI is increasingly deployed in the labour market to recruit, train, and engage employees or monitor for infractions that can lead to disciplinary proceedings, the BIAS project is investigating its use in the labour market. The project is also studying how human and societal biases are potentially reproduced in AI-based systems and developing tools to identify and mitigate these biases.

The dissemination and communication efforts of the BIAS project are designed to support its mission. These efforts have been tailored and implemented to align with the project's evolving needs. In this context, we identify three main stages:

- **1st stage: Knowledge.** The communication strategy focused on conducting a situational analysis of the project and developing its initial strategy.
- **2nd stage: BIAS Strategy.** BIAS partners focused defining a unique identity for the project, setting up relevant tools and channels to be used and starting to create awareness about the project, thereby building a community of stakeholders and target groups.
- **3rd stage: Action Plan.** Undergoing until the end of the project, this stage focuses on the detailed planning of all communication activities, which includes the creation of actions, the definition of their objectives, the definition of the responsible party to carry out each action, the definition of their timings, and the selection and production of the necessary materials.

This deliverable provides detailed information about the channels, materials and tools used to support an effective communication and dissemination of the BIAS project in the period M1 (November 2022) to M24 (October 2024). Further updates of this document will be provided on M48 (D7.4 – Final report on DCE activities).

This deliverable is divided into 7 main sections:

- **Section 3 “Branding”** presents the identity of the project.
- **Section 4 “Channels and tools”** presents the different channels and tools used for disseminating and communicating project activities and outcomes, including the project website and its performance, social media accounts and their paid campaigns, YouTube Channel and all the videos created, email marketing, and media coverage.
- **Section 5 “Events”** describes the communication activities undertaken in BIAS to support the promotion of the events where the project partners have been involved in, either as organisers, participants (i.e., speakers) or attendees.
- **Section 6 “Scientific publications”** presents BIAS partners' publications, including conference papers, journals, books, open datasets.

- **Section 7 “Networking and clustering”** describes all the synergies and collaborations done with other projects and organisations; the creation of the AI Fairness Cluster and all the actions developed by LOBA under its scope; and a detailed description of the results obtained in the Trustworthy AI Helix.
- **Section 8 “Project and community sustainability”** describes the plans already developed for the post-project Trustworthy AI Helix maintenance and the funding synergies already found for the exploitation process of the project.
- **Section 9 “Communication performance against the evaluation criteria”** provides a comparison between the key performance indicators defined in the Description of Action (DoA) and the current status, in order to assess the overall performance of the dissemination and communication activities.
- Finally, **section 10 “Conclusions”** concludes the deliverable.

In addition, the deliverable includes 2 Annexes:

- [Annex 1 - Paid campaigns in social media](#)
- [Annex 2 - Samples of cover images for events](#)

3. Branding

3.1. Project’s Identity

The identity of the project was developed in its early stages (M2) as described in detail in Deliverable D7.1 “Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan”. During this time the identity has been consistently used in all the communication channels, materials, and actions carried out for creating awareness about the project and communicating its activities and results.

The BIAS identity, which comprises not only the logo but also the font type, the colours, and language, is present in the website, social media networks (i.e., X, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, Telegram), stationery (i.e., templates, folders, etc.), communication kit (i.e., brochure, poster, roll-up, pop-up booth, project presentation), images and cards used for publications in social media, promotional video, materials used to promote BIAS’ events or BIAS participation in events (i.e., cover banners, agendas, among other).

Figure 1: BIAS logo with and without claim

Figure 2: Examples of application of BIAS identity

The consistent use of the BIAS identity eases the recognition of the project among the target groups supporting the project in gaining a space within the AI ecosystem.

3.2. Communication toolkit

The communication toolkit developed for the BIAS project comprises the materials that aid the consortium in their formal and informal communication activities, such as reporting and participation in meetings and events, while ensuring promotion of the brand identity by making it memorable.

This toolkit is composed by the project’s stationery and promotional support materials, as explained below.

3.2.1. Project’s Stationery

The stationery produced for the project includes materials to support the communication and reporting of the project, namely:

- Word and PowerPoint templates used for reporting purposes and for presentations at meetings or events (the PowerPoint has two formats: 16x9 and 4x3).
- Supporting materials for participating in events and meetings such as folders, letterhead paper, business cards, background for online meetings, and an email signature for the identification of the project in communications. Badges for identifying participants at events were also created.

Figure 3: BIAS deliverable template

Folder

Letterhead paper

Business cards

Figure 4: BIAS stationery

3.2.2. Promotional material

The promotional support materials developed during the period M1-M24 have been produced for the promotion of the project during the participation in or organisation of events and meetings with relevant stakeholders.

These materials include:

- Brochure and flyer with information about the objectives, activities and expected results of the project.
- Power point presentation of the project for partners to use when participating in events.
- Poster and roll-up to increase the project's visibility in events.
- Sticker to promote the surveys on discrimination, exclusion, and marginalization of workers (created under WP2).

All these materials were printed and distributed among the partners (to be used in project events and activities) and are also available in digital format (accessible on the BIAS website). All partners have been encouraged to use the communication and promotional materials in their dissemination activities, to increase the project awareness and the effectiveness of dissemination actions.

Brochure

Sticker

Poster

Roll-up

Figure 5: BIAS' promotional material

3.2.3. Merchandising

BIAS has also produced a set of goodies, primarily useful in an office context. These include mousepads, pens, stress balls, notebooks, and webcam blockers. The materials were selected based on their usefulness to the project's target groups. They are distributed at events, especially those with a high number of participants.

Mousepad

**Anti-stress
ball**

**Webcam
blocker**

Notebook

Figure 6: BIAS' merchandising

4. Channels and tools

4.1. Website

The activities related to the website design and development are reported under Deliverable D7.1 “Dissemination, Exploitation, Communications Plan”, which describes the process of its creation and development. We hereby report on the contents produced, updates made and website performance. Since the official launch of the website in M5 (March 2023), the content has been continuously updated with news about the progress of the project and relevant events where BIAS is involved in. This activity includes encouraging partners to provide relevant content for the website as instructed in the dissemination and communication plan (Deliverable D7.1).

In addition, new web pages have been created in line with the progress of the project and responding to the communication needs of the project’s activities.

Content-wise the website currently has a total of [40 news articles](#) (Figure 7 and Figure 8) and [5 events pages](#) (Figure 9 and Figure 10).

Figure 7: Screenshot of the news section in BIAS website

Figure 8: Screenshot of the detail web page of a news article

Figure 9: Screenshot of the events section in BIAS website

Figure 10: Screenshot of the detail web page of an event article

Structure-wise, in the period M1 – M24 several new functionalities and pages were created (in addition to the ones available in the original website’s structure) to meet the need for communicating certain project activities:

- **Survey:** This new section of the website was created to encourage participation in the WP2 survey on workers' experiences. The page features a prominent link to the survey at the top, followed by a brief explanation detailing the survey's purpose, target audience, available languages, and where it can be accessed. After the survey closed, the page was unpublished and is no longer visible to the public.

Figure 11: Screenshot of the Survey webpage

- **Consortium:** In addition to featuring an interactive map where users can select partners to learn more about them, the Consortium webpage now includes a section at the bottom with profiles of all partners. This allows users to either explore specific information directly through the map or gain a general overview of everyone involved in the consortium through this new section.

Figure 12: New structure of the Consortium webpage

- Events with photos:** The "External Events" webpage now features an image linked to each event, displayed on the main page, similar to the layout used on the "News and Articles" page. This enhancement makes each event more visually appealing and engaging.

Figure 13: New feature of the "External Events" webpage

- "Results in Brief" with filters:** The BIAS Actionable Knowledge webpage is now better organized with the addition of filters, making it easier to find specific results. Users can filter results by format (e.g., booklet, brochure, factsheet) and by the relevant WP topic (e.g., capacity building, raising awareness for AI and HR communities; stakeholder involvement, needs assessment, co-creation; etc.). This enhancement improves the accessibility and discoverability of the project's resources.

Figure 14: New filtering system of the "Results in Brief" webpage

- “Activities” with filters:** Similarly to the “Results in Brief” webpage, the “Activities” webpage now features a new filtering system designed to enhance the searchability of activities. The filters are organized by country, activity type, and date, making it easier for users to find specific activities.

Figure 15: New filtering system of the “Activities” webpage

- Data Donation:** A new webpage was created to promote the Cover Letter & CV Donation Campaign. The page begins with a brief introduction to the campaign, followed by sections explaining why the campaign matters, what our goals are, and how companies can contribute. Additionally, the page includes a list of eligible countries and provides contact information for companies interested in participating.

Figure 16: Screenshot of the new Data Donation Campaign webpage

4.1.1. Website Performance

In the initial months, the website featured only basic information about the project. However, as the project progressed and activities expanded, the website evolved to include more detailed and complex content. With each communication effort—whether through social media, press releases, mass mailings, newsletters, or other channels—there was a deliberate focus on driving traffic to the website.

Website statistics from November 1st, 2022 to October 18th, 2024, show promising results:

KPIs	Statistics
Users	8,516
Page Views	30,951
Countries	108
First Visits	8,449
User Engagement	8,069
Engagement Rate	50.57%
Bounce Rate	49.43%
Downloads	389

Table 1: Website statistics from November 1st, 2022 to October 31st, 2024

With 8,516 users, 30,951 page views, and visitors from 108 countries, the website attracted a broad international audience. The engagement rate of 50.57% demonstrates strong user interaction with the content, highlighting the effectiveness of our communication strategies. While the bounce rate (percentage of visitors who land on a webpage and leave without taking any further action) of 49.43% suggests opportunities for improvement in retaining visitors, this will be addressed as part of the ongoing strategy to optimize user experience and further engage our growing audience. The website's reach extended across 108 countries, showcasing its global appeal and the project's ability to engage a diverse, international audience. This broad geographical spread is a strong indicator of the project's relevance and impact beyond its immediate stakeholders, positioning it as a key player in the global conversation around AI bias. The diversity of visitors also opens up opportunities for further tailoring content to meet the needs of different regions and cultures, ensuring the project continues to resonate with a wide range of stakeholders.

4.2. Social Media

The official social networks of the BIAS were launched in M2 (December 2022) on Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter (now called X). A YouTube channel has been established as well. More recently,

following internal discussions among the consortium members and recommendations from project reviewers, Instagram and Telegram accounts were created. Instagram aims to engage a younger audience, while Telegram focuses on enhancing community management. Telegram is currently in a testing phase to assess whether it provides tangible value to the project and its target audiences.

The creation of social media channels entailed:

- Definition of appropriate handle @BIASProjectEU and hashtags for the project.
- Definition of other channels to follow (EU accounts, related projects, and initiatives channels, the BIAS's sister projects channels, and the consortium partners channels).
- Design and upload of the cover and profile images.
- Design of frame templates to include pictures in publications.
- Design of frame templates for heading posts (newsletter, presentation of the consortium, presentation of related projects and initiatives, etc.).
- Design of frame templates for posts related to the BIAS events and activities.
- Research-relevant content for our audiences, both from internal sources (within the project) and external (sources outside the project) and development of relevant posts.

Each month, a social media plan is designed defining the weekly publications for each social media channel. At least 2 publications are created per week in each channel, which entails creating images and contents for each publication. Additional posts are also added to the social media plan whenever there is new information (event, activities, announcements) about the project that should be communicated to our followers. At the same time, a lot of attention is given to the engagement and reach on social media channels, continuously retweeting/sharing and interacting with other accounts, like the ones mentioned previously.

During the first period of the project, the focus of the content published in social media has evolved in line with the progress of the project, going from creating awareness about what the BIAS is and what the project has to offer, to communicating specific activities, events, and results, creating affinity with its community and target audiences. Thus, the social media of the project focused on the following communication objectives:

- To inform about BIAS, its objectives, and main activities & initiatives, about events that BIAS is involved in (as well as initiatives linked to them, such as call for papers), about news and articles written by the BIAS consortium, and about AI, HRM and diversity bias.
- To engage our audience towards specific activities with dedicated campaigns (the survey of workers on bias experiences, the co-creation activities, the first awareness raising webinar, the National Labs, the Data Donation Campaign, etc.).

- To support the communication of activities and events from the AI Fairness cluster projects and other partners.
- To share international dates relevant to the BIAS community. An internal spreadsheet was created for this purpose, including all pertinent international dates (e.g., Zero Discrimination Day, International Workers' Day, International Day of Older Persons, etc.). Partners can select the dates they would like to write an article about, and these articles can then be promoted on social media to celebrate the chosen date.
- To share awareness-raising videos and other multimedia content, such as interviews with participants from international co-creation workshops, the "What is Bias" explainer video, and Reels, including those showcasing BIAS partners' New Year's wishes for their WPs or the "Ask Me Anything" videos.
- To promote the project's newsletters and their subscription.
- To create polls that address the BIAS community's questions and engage with them in a more direct and interactive way.
- To promote the project's results and insights by utilizing the Actionable Knowledge materials and turning them into publications that present information in an accessible and engaging way.

Following the project and the partner's needs, it was also created a "Social Media Communication kit" aimed at promoting the survey and the several co-creation workshops, composed of posts' images with call to actions in each partner's language, as well as a description (also translated) to accompany the image and explain more in detail what are the survey and co-creation workshops for. The images were created in different formats, so that they could also be used in the partners' websites and email marketing.

At the start of 2024, to adapt and tailor BIAS's social media strategy to its current needs, a new analysis was made, and a proposal was developed, which included the following:

- Listing the new project objectives for the year.
- Describing the target audiences, now with deeper insights gained throughout the project.
- Creating personas for each target audience.
- Defining the project's tone of voice for each social media platform.
- Reviewing the current KPIs for social media, the website, and the newsletter.
- Listing best practices to implement across the platforms mentioned above. Some have already been implemented (and referenced throughout this deliverable), such as:
 - Creating "Ask Me Anything" videos,

- Launching a Telegram channel to boost community engagement,
- Introducing polls in social media posts,
- Developing a Linktree to centralize the project's main links.
- Defining the key communication phases:
 1. **Create Awareness:** Encourage questions and foster communication and participation in the BIAS Project.
 2. **Share Knowledge:** Provide answers and boost understanding of AI biases in HR practices.
 3. **Maximize Impact:** Empower the community and amplify the project's reach.
- Conducting a benchmark (analysing BIAS sister projects and comparing BIAS's status with theirs).
- Outlining a paid campaign plan for 2024.
- Developing a timeline with the BIAS key activities scheduled for each month of 2024.

4.2.1. Paid campaigns

Social media campaigns play a crucial role in effectively reaching and engaging target audiences on a broad scale. With this in mind, several campaigns were launched during this period (2 on Facebook, 3 on LinkedIn, and 1 on YouTube), including:

- A **followers campaign** on Facebook, LinkedIn, and YouTube to grow the audience on these platforms.
- A **survey promotion campaign** focused on increasing responses to the workers' questionnaire.
- A **National Labs promotion campaign** aimed at boosting registrations and participation in BIAS's stakeholder communities.

These campaigns and their outcomes are listed in [Annex 1 – Paid campaigns in social media](#).

4.2.2. Social media performance

All objectives set for the BIAS social media channels were achieved within the first 24 months of the project, the vast majority of which far exceeded expectations. The analytics of the project's social media in X, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram show a constant increase of followers, and the number in reach and impressions means that the information shared in these channels is reaching a

significant number of people. Thus, the campaigning actions and results described in the previous sections are also reflected in these analytics. However, our goal is not having just statistics but ensure that the people behind those statistics engage with our content, and act such as visiting our website, registering in our events, participating in our activities, or just sharing our content.

Since the creation of the social media networks, BIAS has published 245 posts in X (former Twitter), 246 posts in Facebook and 275 posts in LinkedIn, with an average of 15 posts per month.

BIAS Social Media Overview	
Followers	1,272
Link clicks	3,441
Comments	94
Reach	89,985
Reactions	3,917
Posts	835

Table 2: BIAS social media overview statistics

	Facebook	X	LinkedIn	Instagram
Followers	146	357	630	49
Posts	246	245	275	69
Reactions (likes)	368	1,595	1,709	245
Comments	3	44	47	0
Shares	26	416	66	16
Clicks on recommended links	81	488	2,872	0
People reached	4,434	56,750	26,788	2,013

Table 3: Social media statistics per each channel

Figure 17: Number of followers per each BIAS social media channel

An analysis of the BIAS project's **Facebook** page shows that images published and sponsored in the news feed consistently outperformed other content types. The higher volume of image posts, compared to videos and standard monthly uploads, contributed significantly to these results. Additionally, the use of effective Calls to Action (CTAs) in image posts helped boost engagement.

On **X** (formerly Twitter), the platform saw solid growth, with 357 new followers gained during this period. Despite only running two active campaigns, the primary posts within these campaigns achieved notable metrics in terms of reach and engagement.

LinkedIn proved to be the most effective channel, as campaigns were primarily focused on driving traffic to the BIAS website. It received the highest investment during this period and delivered the strongest results, both in terms of growing social media followers and website visits. As with Facebook, image posts on LinkedIn generated the most reactions and engagement.

Instagram, being one of the most recently adopted channels for the BIAS project, has considerable room for growth. Consequently, its performance so far has been relatively modest compared to other platforms, but there is potential for improvement as the channel develops.

4.3. YouTube channel

The [BIAS YouTube channel](#) was created on Month 1 (November 2022) and has been used mainly as a repository to host the videos promoting the project and the recordings of BIAS online/hybrid workshops and events.

Mitigating biases of AI in the labour market

Figure 18: Screenshot of BIAS's YouTube channel

The BIAS YouTube channel currently has 90 subscribers, 38 videos, and a total of 1,814 views. All the videos have been thoughtfully organised into playlists to enhance the viewer's experience. Each playlist and video are accompanied by a description and information about BIAS. Here, we present the list of videos available in the project's YouTube channel, the playlist they belong to, and the number of views. Shorts have also been considered in this list:

Videos	Playlist	Views
BIAS Project: Our Visual Identity	BIAS Project	176
BIAS - Mitigating biases of AI in the labour market	BIAS Project	135
Addressing Bias in AI for Equality in HR Recap of Estonian Co-Creation Workshop	Co-creation Workshops	74
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Ask Me Anything: How does bias affect AI systems, especially in hiring? (part 1)	Ask Me Anything	10
Ask Me Anything: How does bias affect AI systems, especially in hiring? (part 2)	Ask Me Anything	7
Ask Me Anything: Can AI be protected from bias?	Ask Me Anything	3
Ask Me Anything: Can you tell us more about unconscious bias?	Ask Me Anything	7
Ask Me Anything: What steps can companies take to reduce bias in the workplace?	Ask Me Anything	6
Ask Me Anything: What is the Trustworthy AI Helix? (part 1)	Ask Me Anything	7

Ask Me Anything: What is the Trustworthy AI Helix?	Ask Me Anything	10
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Table 4: Videos uploaded in BIAS' YouTube channel

4.3.1. Videos

BIAS released 38 videos on its [YouTube channel](#) and social media channels and several Reels exclusively on social media. The videos are divided into categories aimed at educating and promoting the project's mission.

Several types of videos were produced, starting with awareness-raising content that explores the fundamentals of bias, fairness, and the use of AI in the labor market, highlighting how these elements intersect. Promotional and tutorial videos were created to introduce the BIAS project, while others focused on showcasing key outcomes, such as co-creation workshops, National Labs, and the Debiaser tool. Additionally, recordings from workshops and events offer in-depth discussions on relevant topics. The videos are detailed below and categorized by the playlists they have been organized into for easier navigation.

BIAS Project

- **[BIAS Project: Our Visual Identity](#)**: The video introduces the branding and visual elements associated with the BIAS project. It explains the concept behind the project's logo, colours, and overall design philosophy, highlighting how these elements reflect the project's core mission and values.
- **[BIAS - Mitigating biases of AI in the labour market](#)**: The video highlights the project's approach to identifying, addressing, and mitigating algorithmic biases that may unfairly impact job seekers. It discusses the challenges of reducing biases in artificial intelligence systems, particularly within the context of employment and hiring. The goal is to promote BIAS's mission related with fairness and inclusivity in AI-driven recruitment processes.
- **[Women's Day](#)**: The video commemorates and celebrates International Women's Day, focusing on recognizing women's contributions and promoting gender equality. It highlights the importance of empowerment, achievements, and the ongoing fight for women's rights across various sectors, namely those that are usually associated with men.

Co-creation Workshops

- **[Addressing Bias in AI for Equality in HR | Recap of Estonian Co-Creation Workshop](#)**: The video provides an overview of a workshop held in Estonia focused on mitigating bias in artificial intelligence within human resources. The video highlights key discussions and

collaborative efforts aimed at creating fairer AI systems for recruitment processes, emphasizing equality and inclusivity in HR practices. This promotional video was initiated by our partner Digiotech, who proactively created and sent it to LOBA, which then handled its editing and publication.

- **[HR Office representative interview: Mario Molinari | International Co-creation Workshop](#)**: The video features an interview with Mario Molinari, an HR representative, discussing the outcomes of the BIAS International Co-creation Workshop. The conversation focuses on the role of human resources in implementing fair AI systems in recruitment and the collaborative efforts made during the workshop to address challenges related to AI biases in the hiring process.
- **[AI Bias in Recruitment and HR | Estonian 2nd Round Co-Creation Workshop Recap](#)**: The video reviews the second round of Co-creation Workshops held in Estonia. It focuses on addressing biases in AI within the context of recruitment and HR, discussing strategies and solutions for creating fairer and more inclusive hiring processes through collaborative efforts and stakeholder engagement.
- **[AI specialist interview: Sigyn Jónsdóttir | International Co-creation Workshop](#)**: The video features an interview with AI specialist Sigyn Jónsdóttir. She discusses her insights and experiences from the International Co-creation Workshop, focusing on the role of AI in recruitment and the challenges of addressing biases in AI systems. The conversation also highlights collaborative approaches to creating fair and inclusive recruitment processes powered by AI.
- **[Workers' representative interview: Anett Numa | International Co-creation Workshop](#)**: The video features Anett Numa, a workers' representative, discussing her experiences and insights from the International Co-creation Workshop. The conversation focuses on the importance of worker representation in discussions around AI, particularly in ensuring fairness and inclusivity in AI-driven recruitment systems. Anett emphasizes the role of collaboration between different stakeholders to address AI biases and improve the hiring process.
- **[Highlights from Venice | BIAS International Co-creation Workshop Recap](#)**: The video provides a summary of key moments and discussions from the BIAS International Co-creation Workshop held in Venice. It highlights collaborative efforts to address and mitigate biases in artificial intelligence, particularly in the context of recruitment and human resources, through stakeholder engagement and shared insights. The recap emphasizes the importance of ensuring fairness and inclusivity in AI-driven systems.

Webinars

- **[Citizen Science and AI Technologies | Webinar](#)**: The video explores the intersection of citizen science and artificial intelligence technologies. It discusses how AI can empower citizen scientists to contribute to research projects, enhance data collection, and enable new discoveries. The webinar also highlights the role of public involvement in scientific innovation, with AI tools supporting collaboration and problem-solving across various fields.

National Labs

- **[Join the BIAS National Labs and shape the future of AI and HR](#)**: The video encourages individuals to participate in the BIAS National Labs initiative. It focuses on the role of these labs in developing and implementing AI solutions that enhance fairness and inclusivity in human resources. The video invites stakeholders to collaborate in shaping AI systems that can positively impact recruitment processes and address biases in AI technologies.

Awareness Videos

- **[What is Bias?](#)**: The video introduces the BIAS project, focusing on its mission to address and mitigate biases in artificial intelligence, especially within human resources and recruitment processes. It explains the importance of developing fair and inclusive AI systems that promote equal opportunities, aiming to ensure that AI technologies do not perpetuate discrimination or unfair practices. The project seeks to bring stakeholders together to collaboratively improve AI-driven HR tools.

AI Fairness Inaugural Conference

The playlist titled "[AI Fairness Inaugural Conference](#)" showcases various sessions and discussions from the inaugural conference dedicated to AI fairness, organised by the AI Fairness Cluster projects. The videos explore topics such as mitigating bias in AI, ethical considerations, the impact of AI on industries like human resources, and collaborative efforts to ensure equitable and transparent AI systems. The aim was to bring together experts and stakeholders to address challenges and innovations in promoting fairness within AI technologies, as well as showcase the work that is being developed by the four projects that compose this cluster.

Ask Me Anything

The playlist "[Ask Me Anything](#)" features short videos where members of the BIAS consortium answer questions related to AI, human resources, and mitigating biases in recruitment processes. The aim is to provide quick, informative insights on how AI can be made fairer and more inclusive.

BIAS interviews and events

- **INCLUSION Festival**: This video highlights BIAS's participation in an online festival dedicated to exploring the intersection of AI, ethics, and fairness in the labour market. It showcases how BIAS contributed to the conversation by discussing key project initiatives, such as promoting fairness in AI-driven recruitment processes and addressing biases in AI tools. The presentation emphasized the project's commitment to fostering a more inclusive and transparent use of AI in human resources, while also engaging with the festival's audience to raise awareness about the importance of ethical AI in shaping the future of work.

In addition to the videos available on the BIAS YouTube channel, several short clips were specifically created for social media. These include videos featuring project partners promoting their respective **National Labs** and clips highlighting **New Year's resolutions for each BIAS Work Package**. The latter feature the partners leading those Work Packages, showcasing their goals and commitments for the year.

4.4. Newsletters and mass mailing

During this period (from Month 1 to Month 24) two newsletters were produced, distributed to the project's mailing lists and promoted in BIAS channels. After the promotion of the newsletter, each article was also promoted individually on social media.

4.4.1. Mailing lists

One of the goals of the BIAS project was to keep developing a strong database of contacts, in accordance with the GDPR and targeting the right audiences. Our database is composed of the following mailing lists:

- BIAS website subscribers: 113
- Co-creation Workshop participants: 175
- National Labs participants: 45
- Capacity-building Session's participants: 22

In total, our database consists of **417¹ contacts**.

4.4.2. Newsletter issue 1 – September 2023

The first newsletter was launched in September 2023 and can be accessed [HERE](#). The main objective of this newsletter was to inform about the project, its main objectives, activities, and the upcoming and past events. Thus, the newsletter comprised the following articles:

- Welcome to BIAS, by Mark Kharas (Project Administrator), from NTNU
- News:
 - National Labs promotion
 - Survey on workers' experience
 - Recap of the Co-creation Workshops first round
 - Trustworthy AI Helix promotion
- Latest findings & results:
 - Early insights about the Debiaser tool
 - The use of Case-Based Reasoning in the BIAS project
 - BIAS promotional video
 - Infographic about the National Labs
- Upcoming events & activities:
 - Co-creation Workshop | Estonia - Second Round (29th September 2023; Online)
 - Co-creation Workshop | Türkiye - Second Round (3rd October 2023; Online)
 - Webinar | Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence Technologies (9th October 2023; Online)
- In case you've missed it:
 - Co-creation Workshops
 - Co-creation Workshop in Estonia
 - BIAS partner talks about stereotypes in word embeddings at TRANSFORM 2023
 - BIAS Official Reports
 - PR "European Commission launches the BIAS project to pioneer a more equal and fair labour market"

¹ Note that these lists are not static and have grown over time.

Figure 19: Screenshot of the BIAS Newsletter #1

4.4.3. Newsletter issue 2 – April 2024

The second newsletter was launched in April 2024 and can be accessed [HERE](#). The primary goal of this newsletter was to highlight the key achievements and progress made during the project's first year and a half. It also aimed to promote the worker survey, the AI Fairness Cluster, and upcoming events and activities, as well as to provide a recap of the International Co-creation Workshop in Venice and the ethnographic interviews. The newsletter featured the following articles:

- Recap of the project's updates, by Roger Søråa (Principal Investigator) & Mark Kharas (Project Administrator), from NTNU
- News:
 - Survey on workers' experience
 - Recap of the International Co-creation Workshop in Venice
 - Presentation of the BIAS ethnographic interviews
 - Presentation of the AI Fairness Cluster
- Upcoming events & activities:
 - Workshop on fairness and diversity bias in AI-driven recruitment (28th May 2024 to 31st May 2024; Hamamatsu, Shizuoka [Japan])
- In case you've missed it:
 - Breaking Ground in AI Fairness: A Glimpse into the Lawtommation Day

- Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence Technologies: Collaborating for an Innovative and Unbiased Future
- Diversity in the Digital Revolution International Day of Women and Girls in Science
- Highlights from Venice BIAS International Co-creation Workshop Recap
- BIAS video to celebrate the International Women's Day
- Interviews to HR, Workers, and AI specialists
- Join the BIAS National Labs and shape the future of AI and HR
- "Mitigating Diversity Biases of AI in the Labor Market" Scientific Publication
- BIAS public reports

Figure 20: Screenshot of the BIAS Newsletter #2

4.4.4. Performance

The newsletters are available in a dedicated BIAS webpage ([HERE](#)). During this period, the newsletter webpage had **506 views** and recorded **1,317 event counts**. With an average of **2.60 events per visitor**, this shows that users are engaging with multiple links, likely navigating to individual newsletter pages. Since the page primarily serves as a gateway to these newsletters, the average engagement time of **30 seconds** is reasonable, as visitors are quickly moving on to explore the actual newsletter content. The results from the distribution of newsletters to BIAS' mailing list subscribers (via a marketing campaign) and their promotion on social media are presented below.

Newsletter issue 1

Marketing campaign	269 recipients	96 opened	15 links clicked
Social media	810 impressions	48 engagements	19 clicks
Website	80 views	34 downloads	

Newsletter issue 2

Marketing campaign	330 recipients	119 opened	22 links clicked
Social media	1.046 impressions	56 engagements	25 clicks
Website	30 views	12 downloads	

4.4.5. Mass mailing

During this period, 14 mass mailings were conducted to inform the BIAS community about key project activities and events, as well as to deliver personalized communication to National Labs stakeholders. Below is a detailed list of these mass emails, including the number of contacts reached, categorized by communications specifically targeted at National Labs stakeholders and those sent to the broader mailing list:

- National Labs stakeholders:
 - Mailing “Welcome to the BIAS National Lab!” , delivered to 57 contacts, 36 opened.
 - Mailing “Invitation to participate in immersive AI training for HR professionals 🇨🇦”, delivered to 245 contacts, 133 opened.
 - Mailing “Your Impact Matters! Join Our Open Call for Success Stories 📧”, delivered to 245 contacts, 110 opened.
 - Mailing “Champion Diversity and Innovation in Your Company!”, delivered 370 contacts, 169 opened.
 - Mailing “Reminder: Your Impact Matters! Join Our Open Call for Success Stories 🕒”, delivered to 278 contacts, 125 opened.
- All the mailing lists:
 - Mailing “🚀 Dive into "Citizen Science and AI Technologies": Join the BIAS Webinar on Oct 9th! 🌐”, delivered to 254 contacts, 113 opened.
 - Mailing “Join the Fight Against Bias in AI: Your Voice Matters!”, delivered to 273 contacts, 154 opened.

- Mailing “Call for Papers: Workshop on Fairness and Diversity Bias in AI-driven Recruitment at JSAI-isAI 2024”, delivered to 307, 79 opened.
- Mailing “Happy holidays from the BIAS project!”, delivered to 307 contacts, 68 opened.
- Mailing “AI Fairness Cluster Inaugural Conference & Workshop on AI Bias 🇪🇺”, delivered to 306 contacts, 128 opened.
- Mailing “For a Fairer Future at Work: Join the BIAS Workshop on May 24th! 📢”, delivered to 333 contacts, 174 opened.
- Mailing “🚀 Are you at Latitude59? Then come pay us a visit at our booth!”, delivered to 308 contacts, 138 opened.
- Mailing “Inside the Black Box: BIAS at the EASST-4S 2024 📺”, delivered to 358 contacts, 173 opened.

4.5. Media coverage

During this period, BIAS has sent 2 press releases to a total of 1,357 media outlets. Below we present the dates, titles and number of contacts they were sent to.

- Announcing the launch of the BIAS project
 - Delivered to 599 contacts
 - 178 opened

Following the distribution of this press release, the [Diginomica](#) online magazine scheduled an interview with Mark-William Kharas, the BIAS coordinator, to understand what is the BIAS project about, to whom is addressed, what are the problems we aim to tackle and how (figure 21).

Figure 21: Screenshot of the Diginomica article with an interview with the BIAS coordinator

- Promoting the National Labs
 - Delivered to 758 contacts
 - 252 opened

5. Events

The engagement of BIAS in events has been notably vibrant, with partners placing particular emphasis on this D&C action form since the project's inception. This focus has been pivotal in establishing a noteworthy presence within the AI and HR landscapes.

Events serve as catalysts, fostering collaboration, visibility, knowledge exchange, and practical impact. Through these interactions, BIAS aspires to leave a lasting imprint in the labour market, contributing to positive societal transformation.

Specifically, participation in events has empowered the project to:

- **Bridging knowledge gaps:** These gatherings bring together technologies developers, policy makers, HR professionals, labour unions, academics, among others, facilitating insights, exchanging ideas, and fostering meaningful discussions.
- **Cultivating collaboration and networking:** Events offer invaluable opportunities for participants to connect with peers, potential partners, and community members, cultivating a collaborative ecosystem extending beyond the project's immediate scope.
- **Amplifying visibility and reach:** Publicising progress and results at events enhances visibility and recognition, reaching a diverse audience.
- **Influencing policy and decision-making:** Presenting findings at conferences and workshops enables direct engagement with policymakers and decision-makers, potentially influencing significant policy changes and promoting evidence-based decisions.
- **Enhancing dissemination reach:** Event participation provides a dynamic and engaging dissemination medium. Live presentations, interactive sessions, and multimedia elements simplify complex concepts, appealing to a broader audience and extending the reach beyond academic circles.

The communication and promotion of BIAS's events has followed the following actions:

- **Communication BEFORE the event:**
 - Inform LOBA about the event (Title, date, location, objective, type of participation (speaker, panel, stand, etc), URL...).

- LOBA uploads the event information on the website.
 - (If applicable) LOBA can design a cover image or banner of the event including save the date, agenda and other images for promoting the speakers, etc.
 - LOBA promotes the event in social media channels.
 - LOBA promotes the event on the AI-on-Demand platform.
 - LOBA includes the event in the Newsletter under “upcoming events” (if the event hasn’t taken place) or creates a personalised email marketing campaign.
 - (If applicable) LOBA sends a press release.
 - LOBA shares the event with BIAS partners, subscribers, other projects/initiatives.
 - Crowdhelix shares the event with the AI Fairness Cluster.
 - Crowdhelix promotes the event on the Trustworthy AI Helix.
 - BIAS’ partners are requested to disseminate the event through their networks and channels (i.e., emails, sharing BIAS posts in partners’ social media, posting in their own channels, publishing information in their websites, blogs and/or Newsletters, etc.).
- **Communication DURING the event:**
 - Partners are encouraged to send pictures and quotes from the event to LOBA to be posted on social media.
 - Partners conduct networking and distribution of promotional materials.
 - Partners fill in the "Event Leads" Excel to record the exact contacts made during the event and how to follow up with them, maximizing the value of our attendance at these events.
- **Communication AFTER the event:**
 - Partner sends a brief report with the main outcomes, insights and conclusions from the event and LOBA uploads a news entry with this information to the website. If relevant, this article is also transformed into a paper that can be printed by the partners and brought to events to bring attention to the work done by the BIAS consortium.
 - If the event has been recorded, the partner can send the file to LOBA to be uploaded in YouTube channel, website and published in social media.

- LOBA includes the event in the Newsletter under “in case you’ve missed it” (if the event has already taken place).
- BIAS’ partners are requested to disseminate the results of the event among their networks and channels (i.e., sharing BIAS posts in social media, posting in their own channels).
- BIAS’ partners should fill in the “D&C Monitor Table” that allows LOBA to track all the important information about the events attended by the consortium and to upload it in the Participants Portal.

During this period project partners have participated in 47 events, reaching approximately 6,600 participants, who were potentially informed about the project activities and findings.

The full list of events and number of participants potentially reached in each event is presented in the table below.

Date	Event title Location Partner	Nr. Participants
9 February 2023	Rollup Exhibition at NTNU European Conference Brussels NTNU	150
24 March 2023	Algorithms for Her? Sheffield ULEID	50-100
31 March 2023	Event Hack4SocialGood Bern BFH	50-100
3 May 2023	Event TRANSFORM 2023 Bern BFH	200
June 2023	General project promotion Tromsø NTNU	90
September 2023	AI Lund Fika-to-Fika Workshop on Regulating High Risk AI in the EU Lund University and online ULEID	>100
September 2023	Lawtimation days IE University ULEID	50-100
September 2023	NGO event: NGO-Koordination post Beijing Schweiz Bern BFH	20-30
September 2023	Event for teachers Bern BFH	50-100
September 2023	Online webinar for postal organisations in Europe Online BFH	80-100

October 2023	HR and Management School Bern BFH	20-30
11 October 2023	"Ethical issues with BIAS and Mitigating diversity of AI in the Labor Market Trondheim NTNU	35
27 October 2023	"Bias in the labor market perpetuated by automation" Los Angeles NTNU	15
November 2023	Management event from the local authorities Bern BFH	20-40
November 2023	Master thesis days at Leiden University Leiden University ULEID	50-100
November 2023	NTNU Innovation Day Online NTNU	30-40
1 November 2023	Bias at Work? Artificial Intelligence in the Recruitment Process Santa Cruz NTNU	25
8 November 2023	"Delegation and the use of AI in Human Resource Management" Honolulu NTNU	25
13 November 2023	AloD Community Forum Bologna LOBA	87
23 November 2023	Presentation to NTNU HR team Trondheim NTNU	200
29 November 2023	Humanities Faculty Innovation Day Hosted by BIAS Project Trondheim NTNU, SVEN	21
15 February 2024	Lecture on AI in HR e workshop with BIAS methodology Trondheim NTNU	15
13 March 2024	ACM Symposium on Computer Science and Law 2024 Boston ULEIDEN, BFH	50
19 - 20 March 2024	AI Fairness Cluster Inaugural Conference & Workshop on AI Bias Amsterdam CHX, LOBA, ULEID, BFH, NTNU	80
25 March 2024	Track Fairness and Bias in AI Applications for the Labor Market at the Applied Machine Learning Days 2024 Lausanne BFH, ULEID	70

28 March 2024	Presentation for a large Swiss company Bern BFH	
10 April 2024	Workshop "BIAS IA: Mitigare l'impatto di pregiudizi e stereotipi nei processi di selezione del personale supportati da IA. Quale formazione?" Venice SVEN	15-20
17 / 18 April 2024	Booth at 2024 NTNU European Conference Brussels NTNU	200
24 April 2024	NTNU Faculty HR group Trondheim NTNU	30
25 April 2024	Faculty researchers on AI topics Online NTNU	25
8 May 2024	Ethic valuation and agency distribution in AI-powered human resource management Graz NTNU	50
10-14 May 2024	Practicum on law and AI - Advanced master (LLM) in law and digital technologies at Leiden University Leiden ULEID, BFH	54
22 May 2024	Computers, Privacy and Data Protection (CPDP) Conference 2024 Brussels ULEID	50
22 / 24 May 2024	Booth at Latitude59 conference Tallinn DIGIOTOUCH	>3000
28 - 29 May 2024	Japanese Society on Artificial Intelligence Symposium 2024 Tokyo ULEID	50
16 July 2024	AI and Ghost Work in Hiring Processes Amsterdam NTNU	35
17 July 2024	Hiring Black Box: Are you better at hiring than AI at 2024 4S/EASST conference Amsterdam NTNU	200
7 - 10 August 2024	IFRWH - International Federation for Research in Women's History Tokyo HI	120
13 September 2024	Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Work Ithaca ULEID	50
19 - 20 September 2024	Law School on Law and Language at the Universita' di Pavia Pavia ULEID	30

24 September 2024	NorwAI Innovate 2024 Poster presentation Trondheim NTNU	100
24 September 2024	Mentioning BIAS project shortly at a Panel Zurich BFH	40-70
26 - 27 September 2024	Lawtimation Days '24 Madrid ULEID	50
10 October 2024	RecSys in HR Conference Bari NTNU	
	AIF (National Association of Trainers) SVEN	
	AIF Veneto-Friuli Venezia Giulia (Regional Branch) SVEN	
	KS conference Oslo NTNU	600

Figure 22: Photos of the BIAS partners in events (from right to left: EASST-4S 2024, AloD Community Forum and ICT-49 Final Event, Latitude59, JSAI Symposium '24)

6. Scientific dissemination

BIAS partners have published 4 papers, available on the BIAS website in a dedicated page for scientific papers. In the following table, we provide a full list of the publications authored by BIAS partners in the period M1-M24. For each publication, besides the typical paper information, we also provide partners involved, type of publication (journal, conference, book, etc.) and the links where it is possible to find them.

Nr.	Partner	Paper information	Link	Date	Type
1	ULEID	Fairness, AI & Recruitment	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0267364924000335?via%3Dihub	April 2023	Article in journal
2	ULEID, BFH	Carlotta Rigotti, Alexandre Puttick, Eduard Fosch-Villaronga and Mascha Kurpicz-Briki, Mitigating Diversity Biases of AI in the Labor Market.	https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3442/paper-47.pdf	September 2023	-
3	BFH	Alexandre Puttick, Leander Rankwiler, Catherine Ikae, Mascha Kurpicz-Briki, The BIAS Detection Framework: Bias Detection in Word Embeddings and Language Models for European Languages.	https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.18689	26 July 2024	Other
4	BFH	Leander Rankwiler, Mascha Kurpicz-Briki, Evaluating Labor Market Biases Reflected in German Word Embeddings	https://www.swisstext.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Proceedings_Preprint.pdf	June 2024	-

Table 5: Full list of scientific publications

In addition, a [BIAS Zenodo account](#) and community have been created recently to ensure that all the project's scientific papers are available and accessible even after the project ends.

7. Networking and clustering

7.1. Related projects and initiatives

The BIAS project is a member of the AI Fairness Cluster, which brings together four Horizon Europe-funded projects with similar goals and interests: [AEQUITAS](#), [FINDHR](#), [MAMMOTH](#), and **BIAS**. These projects share four key missions: raising awareness about bias in AI systems and mitigating it, organizing forums to address common issues, developing a network to provide input to the European Commission by identifying shared challenges, and promoting innovative solutions to streamline their adoption and use.

The cluster has developed a common visual identity which aims to:

- Clearly demonstrate a joint commitment to "European excellence in trustworthy AI."
- Maintain the distinct identities of individual entities.
- Be easily recognisable and applicable.
- Extend its adoption beyond AI Fairness.
- Offer a symbol that can serve as a unifying modifier.

The design of the logo and guidelines has been a collaborative effort between the AI Fairness projects and the European Commission. It draws inspiration, in part, from the logo developed by UCC and LOBA for the AI-on-Demand platform. The logo is designed to be used at the same time integrated with logos of the cluster projects.

01. logo . integration with project identity

Figure 23: AI Fairness Cluster Logo and its integration with project identities

In addition to the visual identity, a communication kit was designed to serve the following functions:

- Standardizing the internal and external communication within the cluster.

- To have ready-to-use templates to facilitate the dissemination of information, helping to amplify the project's impact.
- To have standardized dissemination materials ready for the time efficiency.
- To foster the visibility of each member project of the cluster.

The communication kit, which was developed and approved by the AI Fairness cluster members, includes the most used visibility and dissemination / presentation materials such as flyers, roll-ups, PPT templates and word templates. These materials are intended to convey the cluster's goals, discoveries, and projects in an efficient manner. By making these widely used resources available, the cluster makes sure that all participants can utilize AI Fairness Cluster branding and messaging, which promotes cooperation and strengthens outreach initiatives to involve a range of audiences in conversations around AI equity. Some examples of the developed communication kit items are as follows:

Figure 24: AI Fairness Cluster - Flyer

Figure 25: AI Fairness Cluster – Roll-Up

In order to maintain a common platform for efficient dissemination of the cluster activities, a [YouTube channel](#) has been set up where video recordings of past webinars, workshops, and presentations by experts in the field have been published. This channel serves as a platform for sharing knowledge and fostering community engagement.

Figure 26: AI Fairness Cluster YouTube Channel

Along with the other channels of dissemination, a website (<https://aifairnesscluster.eu/>) has been established by the cluster. The website of the AI Fairness Cluster acts as a focal point for advancing AI research on fairness, encouraging cooperation between cluster projects AEQUITAS, FINDHR, MAMMOth, BIAS and other initiatives. The website's goal is to promote studies and solutions that deal with bias and discrimination in AI systems. It offers a space for exchanging project results, sharing information, and promoting cluster events.

Figure 27: AI Fairness Cluster Website

The website seeks to foster the adoption of fairness principles across a range of AI applications by bringing together researchers, politicians, and industry stakeholders. It also makes it easier to have conversations about moral principles and transparency in AI. Through papers, workshops, conferences, and news, the platform facilitates the cluster's interaction with the larger AI community. The BIAS project consortium, in collaboration with other cluster projects, has participated in regular meetings with them. Some meetings focus on the joint activities and outcomes to be developed by the consortium, while others are attended only by the Dissemination & Communication teams of each project to discuss relevant topics related to the cluster's promotion. The next cluster meeting is scheduled for 16.11.2024. Furthermore, communication among cluster members has been actively maintained through email exchanges for joint activities and mutual support requests.

In addition to these, the **AI Fairness Cluster Inaugural Conference and AI Fairness Cluster Workshop** took place on **19th - 20th March 2024 at Science Park Congress Center, Amsterdam (The Netherlands)**, as the AI Fairness Cluster Inaugural Conference aimed to address the risks and difficulties of bias in recruitment processes by AI systems, especially in relation to fairness,

discrimination, and reliability. **The conference**, which took place on the 19th of March and brought together specialists from several Horizon Europe projects, explored the technical, legal, and societal implications of AI fairness. The goal of the conference was to promote dialogue, showcase innovative research, and create plans for mitigating bias in AI. The workshop, **AIMMES'23** (AI Biases: Measurements, Mitigation, Explanation Strategies), which took place on the 20th of March, aimed to foster a technical dialogue and deepen understanding of the challenges and opportunities at the intersection of AI, fairness, and bias in our rapidly evolving technological landscape. The keynotes for both events are as follows:

1. AI Fairness Cluster Inaugural Conference: 19 March 2024

Both the technical and social/legal facets of AI fairness were the main topics of the first conference. Ivana Bartoletti from Wipro spoke about the technical sides of AI fairness, while Joanna Goodey from the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights addressed the social and legal aspects. Research from AEQUITAS, BIAS, FINDHR, and MAMMOth was presented in the project presentations. The event continued with 2 Panels:

- Panel 1: Roger Søråa (BIAS) led the discussion of "Representational Harms in Foundation Models," which included Payal Arora and Nicu Sebe as experts.
- Panel 2: Carlos Castillo (FINDHR) hosted this session, which covered "Discrimination Risks in AI Decision-Making," and featured speakers Eirini Ntoutsi and Krishna Gummedi.

2. Workshop on AI Bias: Measurements, Mitigation, Explanation Strategies, 20 March 2024

As part of its efforts to further research on AI fairness, the AI Fairness Cluster hosted a technical workshop titled "AI Bias: Measurements, Mitigation, and Explanation Strategies" (AIMMES'24) on March 20, 2024, in Amsterdam. The workshop's main goals were to promote technical discussion and advance knowledge of the difficulties associated with bias in AI systems. The topics of interest for the workshop were announced in prior to the event as follows:

Measuring Bias

- Novel AI bias and fairness definitions, human factors in AI bias
- Role of social sciences, law and humanities in bias definition
- Involving vulnerable and under-represented communities in bias definition
- Measuring and studying bias in multi-attribute and multimodal settings

Mitigating Bias

- Methods for exploring trade-offs across multiple notions of fairness and accuracy
- Use of synthetic data for bias mitigation
- Fairness-aware ranking and recommendation

- Application-specific mitigation approaches for hiring, credit scoring, face recognition, etc.

Paper presentations on fairness in healthcare datasets, ethical issues in large language models, and bias in algorithmic hiring were presented. The paper by Seán Healy on fair re-ranking techniques, research on prejudice in algorithmic hiring by Alessandro Fabris and colleagues, the study on fairness intervention techniques in ranking systems by Clara Rus and Maarten de Rijke were among the highlighted papers. Regarding the sessions for posters, technical remedies for prejudice, difficulties with AI decision-making, and the ethical ramifications of AI in fields like healthcare and employment were all covered in two poster sessions. The event promoted cooperation between initiatives and organizations aimed at guaranteeing just, reliable AI systems and highlighted continuing efforts to prevent AI bias. The workshop has been attended by 111 participants from different organizations working on various domains related to AI systems, mitigation of bias and fairness in AI. The conference and the workshop have contributed significantly to the advancement of AI fairness. Both events encouraged interdisciplinary knowledge sharing and cooperation on the topic of bias in AI systems by bringing together researchers working on related topics. Important subjects such as identifying, and reducing bias were covered, with an emphasis on offering useful tactics that can be used in actual AI systems.

Additionally, the event was crucial in carrying the AI Fairness Cluster community one step further by encouraging new relationships and possible long-term partnerships among attendees. It is anticipated that these partnerships will lead to cooperative research initiatives and publications that will advance the field of AI fairness studies. Furthermore, the conversations that took place throughout the session are expected to have an impact on future AI policy, especially when it comes to ethical AI development, helping to create guidelines that support fairness, responsibility, and inclusivity.

The workshop will have other effects for the development and implementation of AI systems in addition to its academic and research contributions. It will surely help in the development of more just and equitable AI systems by providing researchers and developers with improved instruments and techniques to identify and reduce bias, specifically thanks to the outputs of cluster-member projects. In addition to fortifying the AI Fairness Cluster's basis, this event lays the groundwork for future advancements and innovation for using of AI fairer and more transparent.

Figure 28: Poster “AI Fairness Cluster Inaugural Conference, 19th-20th March 2024”

In addition to joint activities within the cluster, the BIAS project established collaboration with other initiatives that share similar goals, such as the EU-funded [AI-on-Demand \(AIoD\)](#) platform which acts as a community-driven channel for the AI sector. To improve the visibility of its actions and results, BIAS has posted one news article and four events on the platform as part of the project's dissemination strategy. In addition to helping us reach a wider audience within the AI community, this collaboration with AIoD is consistent with our dedication to encouraging transparent collaboration and disseminating project advancements. The platform encourages more discussion and knowledge sharing by providing a chance to highlight the BIAS project's contributions to AI fairness and bias prevention.

The BIAS project also collaborates with [DIVERSIFAIR](#), an Erasmus project which focuses on addressing intersectional fairness in AI across the European Union (EU). A joint webinar organised under WP5 - Capacity building and raising awareness for AI and HR community is planned for 10

December 2024, at 3 PM CET titled “Intersectional Fairness in AI: Legal Frameworks, Tools, and Learning Opportunities”.

Meanwhile, Crowdhelix has reached out to the [AI, Data, Robotics Forum/European Sovereignty in AI, Data, and Robotics](#), which will take place on November 4-5, 2024. BIAS aims to sponsor the event to expand the BIAS network and contribute to the project’s dissemination and exploitation efforts. A joint helix event on Trustworthy AI has been proposed to the event coordinators.

In addition, a cooperative communication has been established between the BIAS project and [IAMASIGUAL](#) program aimed at advancing inclusion and equality. By focusing on common values and sharing materials that increase awareness of intersectional fairness in AI, this collaboration sought to strengthen outreach initiatives. By means of this collaboration, both initiatives benefited from each other's networks, enhancing their influence on stakeholders that are interested in technology and equality. In that sense a series of online meetings and e-mail exchanges took place. The communication is intended to be continued for up-coming activities of both projects.

Finally, **seven other projects** have been identified and were contacted for possible clustering activities. These initiatives address a range of topics related to artificial intelligence and emerging technologies, including research ethics (iRECS, SHERPA, SIENNA), ICT legal adaption (Panelfit), ethical evaluation of new technologies (TechEthos), and the development of objective AI (NoBIAS). **Adra-e** is also in favour of creating a sustainable AI ecosystem in Europe. These partnerships collectively seek to further BIAS's objective of promoting just and moral AI practices throughout Europe.

7.2. Trustworthy AI Helix

As part of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities under WP7, Crowdhelix has been managing the [Trustworthy AI Helix](#) designed to bring together at least 150 relevant stakeholders working on multidisciplinary topics related to AI fairness in recruitment processes. The goal is to foster synergies for both dissemination and exploitation of results, as well as to facilitate joint activities. This virtual ecosystem functions as an online platform where experts from research and innovation organizations, along with SMEs, can collaborate through the following:

- Keeping up to date with the BIAS project via direct announcements.
- Contributing to the project by participating in research and campaigns.
- Collaborating with other stakeholders through personal messaging or public comments.
- Offering new collaboration opportunities and forming new consortiums.

- Receiving early access to BIAS project results and outputs.

By Month 24, the Trustworthy AI Helix, managed by Crowdhelix, had achieved the following milestones:

- 405 experts.
- 189 organizations.
- 44 countries.

With the target number of organizations reached, the helix has achieved a strong balance between Research and Technology Organizations (RTOs) and SMEs. Additionally, a diverse range of associate, corporate, and specialist member organizations from 44 different countries have joined. A detailed update on the distribution of users by organization type, geographic location, and subscription status is provided below.

Figure 29: Number of users by organization type

Figure 30: User subscription graphic (Date range: Launch of the helix – 29 Jul 2024)

Figure 31: Helix users by geographical location

The helix is equally used as a tool to support the dissemination and exploitation of results, as well as announcements on project activities. Since its launch on April 2023, 37 collaboration opportunities, 2 results, 5 events and 3 announcements have been shared through the platform.

Figure 32: Announcement / Result Examples on the Trustworthy AI Helix (<https://platform.crowdhelix.com/helixes/trustworthy-ai>)

8. Project and community sustainability

8.1. Post-project Trustworthy AI Helix maintenance

The Trustworthy AI Helix, maintained by BIAS project partner Crowdhelix, aims to promote and encourage continued cooperation to sustain reliable AI systems. After the project concludes, efforts will focus on maintaining stakeholder alliances, ensuring ongoing development, and addressing new challenges in AI accountability and justice. This includes establishing routine monitoring systems, promoting information sharing, and engaging with various communities to adapt processes based on practical feedback. By leveraging the Helix network, the BIAS project can ensure that AI systems remain robust, dependable, and aligned with ethical principles.

Crowdhelix is committed to maintaining the Helix for at least two years after the project ends. When the BIAS project concludes, the Helix will continue to be hosted on CHX's platform, allowing experts and researchers from a variety of organizations to retain their accounts for free as external users. Additionally, they will have the option for their organizations to join as full members of the network. The Helix Manager will identify a research and technology organization (RTO) member from the Helix who is interested in strategically leading the Helix after the project ends.

8.2. Funding synergies for exploitation

The BIAS project has been developing strategies for consortium building by identifying stakeholders for joint activities, such as members of the AI Fairness Cluster and other related projects and initiatives. These efforts aim to support post-project funding through the formation of potential consortia. To assist with this process, a basic tool has been developed to record potential stakeholders, containing information on various clustering projects related to the BIAS project.

The tool categorizes stakeholders into two main groups: Related Projects/Initiatives and Clusters. Each entry includes details such as the coordinator, project end date, subject focus, website, and clustering name. For tracking purposes, it also includes an ID and Cordis references. To enhance networking and collaboration opportunities, the tool provides a list of participating BIAS partners along with their LinkedIn and Twitter profiles. This systematic approach supports the project's outreach efforts and helps in identifying potential stakeholders. Below is a summarized list of the identified stakeholders:

Clustering Sister Projects:

AEQUITAS	https://www.aequitas-project.eu/	AEQUITAS project will develop a controlled experimentation environment to help AI producers to increase awareness of bias produced by AI systems and evaluate and (possibly) repair existing AI systems.
FINDHR	https://findhr.eu/	FINDHR project will facilitate the prevention, detection, and management of discrimination in algorithmic hiring and closely related areas involving human recommendation.
MAMMOth	https://mammoth-ai.eu/	MAMMOth project tackles bias by focusing on multi-discrimination mitigation for tabular, network and multimodal data.

Other Related Projects / Initiatives:

iRECS	https://www.irecs.eu/	iRECS will first scan and map existing needs raised by new and emerging technologies in European and global research ethics communities. Second, it will produce and implement training materials for European and global audiences in research ethics communities. Third, it will conduct and permanently establish training programmes. Fourth, it will propose adaptations to the research ethics process in Europe.
SHERPA	https://www.project-sherpa.eu/	SHERPA project will investigate, analyse and synthesise our understanding of the ways in which smart information systems (SIS; the combination of artificial intelligence and big data analytics) impact ethics and human rights issues.
SIENNA	https://www.sienna-project.eu/	The SIENNA project addressed ethical issues in three new and emerging technology areas: human genomics, human enhancement and human-machine interaction.
Panelfit	https://www.panelfit.eu/	PANELFIT is a H2020 EU funded project aiming at facilitating the adaptation processes between new technical advances and legal frameworks, by producing a set of editable, openly accessible guidelines, as well as offering operational standards capable of reducing ethical and legal problems posed by information and communication technologies.
TechEthos	https://www.techethos.eu/	TechEthos project will review emerging technologies and the ethical issues these raise.
AI4EUROPE	https://www.ai4europe.eu/	The EU-funded AI4EUROPE project, in collaboration with DeployAI and other related projects, aims to develop this space by introducing an unbiased, open and cooperative platform from and for the European research community for excellent studies of AI
NoBIAS	https://nobias-project.eu/	NoBIAS will develop novel methods for AI-based decision making without bias by taking into account ethical and legal considerations in the design of technical solutions. The core objectives of NoBIAS are

		to understand legal, social and technical challenges of bias in AI-decision making, to counter them by developing fairness-aware algorithms, to automatically explain AI results, and to document the overall process for data provenance and transparency.
Adra-e	https://adra-e.eu/	Adra-e supports the AI, Data and Robotics Association and Partnership to create the conditions for a sustainable European ecosystem

Table 6: Identified Stakeholders

By expanding networking opportunities and contributing cross-sector expertise, the identified stakeholders participating in the BIAS project activities provide substantial advantages for exploitation. Their existing networks can increase the project's visibility, and their knowledge can help shape best practices in AI fairness. Collaborating with these stakeholders not only improves project outcomes but also fosters sustainability and a greater impact in AI fairness.

To guarantee the durability and ongoing advancement of the Trustworthy AI Helix, the BIAS project's exploitation plan focuses on utilizing the experience of its partners. Every partner is essential to this strategy:

- **DIGI:** Supporting the outreach and communication efforts to advance the Helix's goals, DIGI is a crucial partner complementing Crowdhelix' activities. To enable stakeholder participation and make sure that information about the Helix reaches a wide audience, they will make use of their vast network and digital platforms. Additionally, DIGI will offer technical assistance to create training materials and programs that enable stakeholders to take an active role in the Helix, encouraging cooperation and mutual learning.
- **Crowdhelix:** As the key upholder of the Trustworthy AI Helix, Crowdhelix will oversee stakeholder ties and guarantee productive cooperation between registered experts / participants. As part of their duties, they will plan frequent gatherings, webinars, and updates on new developments in AI, encouraging community members to get involved. To facilitate continued communication and information exchange between organizations and specialists, Crowdhelix is dedicated to sustaining the Helix for a minimum of two years after the project concludes.
- **LOBA:** The partner's research and implementation experience will be crucial in amplifying the Helix's dissemination and visibility outputs. By supporting the workshops and joint initiatives, they will actively involve the community in the development of sustainable AI practices. The participation of LOBA will guarantee that the Helix not only stays relevant but also offers new opportunities and synergies among the possible stakeholders.

9. Communication performance against the evaluation criteria

According to the BIAS Description of Action (DoA), the Key Performance Indicators related to the communication and dissemination, which have been periodically monitored, are presented below. Table 5 presents the current status, including the indicators that have already been reached or surpassed and those where we have to work on.

TOOLS & CHANNELS	METRIC METHOD	EXPECTED RESULTS IN TOTAL AT M24	2 ND YEAR RESULTS (M1 - M24)	STATUS
WEBSITE	Website user	1500	8,516	✓
	Total page views	5000	30,951	✓
	Countries reached	10	108	✓
PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS	Number distributed at events and meetings	1,000	3,000	✓
FACTSHEETS	Factsheets produced	3	2	⚠
SOCIAL MEDIA (SOME)	Total Followers	500	1,272	✓
	Posts	60	835	✓
	Clicks to the website through SoMe posts	100	3,441	✓
PRESS RELEASES	Press releases distributed	2	2	✓
NEWSLETTERS AND MAILING LIST	Mailing list subscribers	300	417	✓
	Newsletters sent	2	2	✓
	Newsletter views (in website)	150	110	⚠
	National lab e-mails	5	5	✓
PROMOTIONAL VIDEOS	Number of videos	3	38	✓
	Views: YouTube, SoMe, website	500	1,814	✓
	# of events presented at	4	47	✓
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS, WHITE PAPERS	Papers published or submitted	4	4	✓
POPULAR MEDIA ARTICLES	Number of articles published	30	40	✓
EXTERNAL EVENTS	Number of events attended to disseminate the project	8	47	✓

CLUSTERING WITH RELATED PROJECTS	No. of projects liaised	>10	14	✔
	with			

Table 7: BIAS KPIs status

Based on this analysis, it can be concluded that the project has successfully met almost all its KPIs, particularly in areas such as social media engagement and event participation. Even in areas requiring additional effort, such as driving traffic to the web platform and increasing video views, the KPIs have not only been met but surpassed. The KPI related to the production of factsheets will be achieved by M25 with the release of the "BIAS Co-Creation Workshops: Insights and Results" factsheet, which experienced a slight delay due to higher-priority tasks within the project. The KPI for newsletter views on the website will be addressed through a paid social media campaign, directing people to the BIAS newsletter page, where they can subscribe and access past newsletters.

10. Conclusions

Almost all dissemination and communication related KPIs of the project have been reached, and most of them have largely surpassed the expected numbers. For the success of the project, we put our efforts beyond the expected activities and KPIs, for example, by developing engaging materials and content and conducting consistent and multi-channel communication of activities and events. Additionally, WP7 has been actively supporting all other work packages in the project. For instance, in WP2, it developed a robust communication strategy to promote the survey on workers and attract members to the newsletters. In WP3, it created materials to spread the word about the Data Donation Campaign. In WP4, it launched the #BIASonthemove communication strategy to highlight the ethnographic interviews. In WP5, it led the promotion of the first Capacity-building Session, successfully drawing in more participants. This collaborative effort extends across the entire project. Throughout BIAS duration, we implemented some actions that we believe can serve as recommendations for best practices in dissemination activities, which we present below.

1. **Comprehensive branding and visual identity:** Establishing a strong visual identity early on helped create consistent recognition across all communication channels. The use of a unified branding toolkit—encompassing logos, templates, brochures, and social media frames—ensured that all materials aligned with the project’s mission. This consistent branding enhanced project visibility and made it easier to connect with diverse audiences.
2. **Engaging Digital Platforms:** The BIAS website and YouTube channel became central hubs for information dissemination. The website's content was strategically updated to keep pace with project developments, while new features such as filters for the "Actionable Knowledge" and "Activities" sections made resources more accessible. On YouTube, videos like project updates, co-creation workshop recaps, and expert interviews were thoughtfully organized into playlists, contributing to higher engagement and broader reach.
3. **Targeted social media campaigns:** Social media was a cornerstone of the project’s dissemination efforts. Each month, detailed social media plans were developed, tailoring content to key milestones and events. Posts were not only informative but also interactive, using tools like polls and video series to engage the community. Paid campaigns further amplified the project’s reach, resulting in a marked increase in followers and interactions on platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter.
4. **Active participation in events and conferences:** BIAS partners played a prominent role in numerous scientific and professional events, such as workshops, conferences, and webinars. These events were crucial for fostering collaborations, raising the project’s profile, and sharing insights. Events like the AI Fairness Cluster Conference and the “Hiring Black Box”

allowed the consortium to directly engage with AI researchers, HR professionals, and policymakers, contributing to a richer dialogue on AI fairness.

5. **Building a knowledge-sharing ecosystem:** A major success of the project was the creation of the AI Fairness Cluster and the Trustworthy AI Helix, which connected BIAS to other initiatives and experts in the field. These collaborative networks provided an invaluable platform for sharing knowledge and promoting collective progress on AI fairness, ensuring that the project's contributions would extend beyond its timeline.
6. **Multi-level stakeholder engagement:** The project's ability to engage with a broad spectrum of stakeholders—from AI developers and HR professionals to policymakers and the general public—was a testament to its tailored dissemination approach. By organizing National Labs and facilitating workshops, BIAS created forums for these stakeholders to directly contribute to shaping AI technologies and addressing biases.
7. **Sustained engagement through newsletters and mass mailing:** BIAS maintained consistent communication with its audience through newsletters and mass mailings, ensuring stakeholders remained informed about the project's progress. Personalized communications with key stakeholders, such as National Labs members, proved highly effective in fostering sustained engagement.

11. Annexes

11.1. Annex 1 - Paid campaigns in social media

The following table lists BIAS's paid campaigns in social media in the period M1-M24.

Date	Channel	Type of campaign	Results	Segmentation
12 May 2024 – 29 June 2024	Facebook	First Followers Campaign: Awareness, Engagement with the posts (likes, retweets, replies) and clicks (to profile)	Reach 278,376 people in total (5,678 people a day)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > All genders > 22 to 55 years > Europe (all countries) > Interests: Artificial intelligence, Human resource management, Machine learning, Activism, Social change, Technology, Politics and social issues, Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Programmer, Application Developer, Entrepreneurs, Developers, Investors, Politics, Networking, Labor Unions, Academics, Think Tank, Equality, Diversity and similar subjects.
3 – 31 May 2023	Facebook	Survey Campaign: Awareness, Engagement with the posts (likes, retweets, replies) and clicks (to profile)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Reach 148,536 people in total > Impressions: 1,664.074 in total (16,313.47 a day) > Followers: 201 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > All genders > 22 to 55 years > Europe (all countries) > Interests: Artificial intelligence, Human resource management, Machine learning, Activism, Social change, Technology, Politics and social issues, Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Programmer, Application Developer, Entrepreneurs, Developers, Investors, Politics, Networking, Labor Unions, Academics, Think Tank, Equality, Diversity and similar subjects.
12 May 2024 – 27 May 2024	LinkedIn	First Followers Campaign: Awareness and clicks (to the page)	Impressions: 81,279	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > All genders > 25 to 55 years > Europe (all countries) > Interests: Artificial intelligence, Human resource management, Machine learning, Activism, Social change, Technology, Politics and social issues, Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Programmer, Application Developer, Entrepreneurs, Developers, Investors, Politics, Networking, Labour Unions, Academics, Think Tank, Equality, Diversity and similar subjects.
5 April 2023 – 15 July 2023	LinkedIn	National Labs Campaign: Awareness	Impressions: 28,966	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > All genders > 25 to 55 years

		and clicks (to the page)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Europe (all countries) > Interests: Artificial intelligence, Human resource management, Machine learning, Activism, Social change, Technology, Politics and social issues, Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Programmer, Application Developer, Entrepreneurs, Developers, Investors, Politics, Networking, Labour Unions, Academics, Think Tank, Equality, Diversity and similar subjects.
9 June 2023 – 15 July 2023	LinkedIn	Survey Campaign: Awareness and clicks (to the page)	Impressions: 46,346	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > All genders > 25 to 55 years > Europe (all countries) > Interests: Artificial intelligence, Human resource management, Machine learning, Activism, Social change, Technology, Politics and social issues, Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Programmer, Application Developer, Entrepreneurs, Developers, Investors, Politics, Networking, Labour Unions, Academics, Think Tank, Equality, Diversity and similar subjects.
12 May 2024 – 22 June 2024	YouTube	First Followers Campaign: Awareness, views and subscribers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Reach 46,378 people in total (1,105,19 people per day) > Subscribers: 88 > Views: 1,272 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > All genders > Europe (all countries) > Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Human resource, Machine learning, Activism, Social change, Technology, Politics and social issues, Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Application Developer, Politics, Networking, Labour Unions, Think Tank, Equality, Diversity and Google Ads ideas.

11.2. Annex 2 - Samples of cover images for events

In the following section, we provide some samples of cover images or banners, designed specifically for events that BIAS partners (co)organised in the period M1-M24.

Figure 33: 7th NTNU European Conference

Figure 34: Algorithms for Her Conference

Figure 35: Hack4SocialGood Event

Figure 36: Symposium on Artificial Intelligence

Figure 37: AI Lund Fika-to-Fika Workshop on EU AI Regulation

Figure 38: Lawtotation Days

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Consortium

NTNU

UNIVERSITY
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